

Taking action to prevent and mitigate pollution of groundwater bodies

1 November 2022- 30 April 2026

Grant Agreement no. 101081865

D 6.1: NINFA Promotional material and website

WP	WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation			
Author(s)	Ioanna Thomatou (CETRI)			
Contributor(s)	Francisco Julia			
Reviewer(s)	Author Name (Partner Organisation Name)			
Deliverable nature	Report			
Dissemination level (Confidentiality)	Public (PU)			
Date of delivery	Contractual	31-January-2023	Actual	20-February-2023
Version	Final Version			
Total number of pages	13			
Keywords	Groundwater, pollutants, climate change, monitoring, DSS, sensors aquifer recharge, water treatment, hydrogeology			

Document History

Issue Date	Version	Action
9-February-2023	V0.1	Initial version
20-February-2023	V1.0	Final Version for Submission

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“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101081865”. The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Partners short names

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	COO	LEITAT	ACONDICIONAMIENTO TARRASENSE ASSOCIACION	ES
2	BEN	CETRI	CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (CETRI) LTD	CY
3	BEN	IMT	INSTITUT MINES-TELECOM	FR
4	BEN	WETSUS	STICHTING WETSUS, EUROPEAN CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE FOR SUSTAINABLE WATER TECHNOLOGY	NL
5	BEN	WINGS	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE	EL
6	BEN	Deltares	STICHTING DELTARES	NL
7	BEN	UNIROMA1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA	IT
8	BEN	AQUALIA	FCC AQUALIA SA	ES
8.1	AE	HIDROTEC	HIDROTEC TECNOLOGIA DEL AGUA SL	ES
9	BEN	AYTO ALCÁZARES	AYUNTAMIENTO DE LOS ALCAZARES	ES

Executive Summary

The NINFA Deliverable D6.1 describes the communication tools that have been created since the project's inception to promote and share information about the project and its activities to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community, informing and reaching out to society, and showing the importance of preventing GW contamination while protecting its quality.

A range of promotional materials have been designed to disseminate information about NINFA's initiatives and to attract the interest of a diverse range of stakeholders – including water industry, farming industry, policy makers, technology providers, universities and research networks, investors, media, other EU projects (funded under the same Call) and the wider public.

The project's website (www.ninfa-project.eu) has been launched at the beginning of the project and social media channels have been introduced as part of the project's outreach efforts and to present the objectives, the challenges and the consortium as a whole.

The website and social media channels have a dual purpose: first, to increase public knowledge of the project by providing updates on ongoing research, innovations, training, events, and publications; second, to facilitate the distribution of project outputs and encourage stakeholder feedback, thereby promoting the dissemination and utilization of project outcomes.

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1.Introduction

The goal of Deliverable D 6.1 is to present the promotional material and website that have been developed by the WP6 leader CETRI in a comprehensive manner, with the aim of raising visibility and awareness of the project and its objectives.

The Deliverable is part of Task 6.2 “Dissemination and Communication tools design and development”. It is worth noting that the benefits of Deliverable D6.1 will extend to all WP6 tasks, and even to all the project’s work load, as all partners will rely on the utilization of NINFA’s promotional materials and the website’s communication functions and features.

The NINFA promotional material, website and social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram) are CETRI’s responsibility. The task of regularly updating the NINFA website and keeping the project's social media platforms active will be undertaken by CETRI.

To achieve targeted dissemination of project information to various stakeholder groups, the NINFA website serves as the primary communication and dissemination tool. Additionally, the interactive social media channels enable easy communication and contact with the NINFA community.

2. Promotional Materials - Visual Identity

The term "promotional material," refers to any type of information related to the NINFA project that has been produced by the consortium for the purpose of sharing and communicating information about the project. This information can be written or printed documents, graphics, electronic media, or video presentations.

Several promotional materials have been developed to support the communication of the project's progress and raise awareness of the project.

The materials reflect a common visual identity that has been developed in the first three months of the NINFA project. All materials will be used for the NINFA project and furthermore for the network that will be implemented during the project's lifetime and beyond.

The project's visual identity has been designed by WP6 Leader CETRI and incorporated into project document templates: deliverables, meeting agenda, meeting minutes, and PowerPoint presentation and have been uploaded in the EXT-NINFA Microsoft Teams folder, accessible to all partners.

The NINFA promotional materials that have developed so far are:

- NINFA Logo and color guide
- NINFA Deliverable template
- NINFA Presentation template
- NINFA Agenda template
- NINFA Minutes template
- NINFA Leaflet

2.1. Ninfa Logo

After the kick-off meeting, CETRI proposed five different logo designs and all partners were asked to vote their preference. The winner logo was distributed to the whole consortium and various file formats for different uses (website, leaflet, social channels), were uploaded in the EXT-NINFA Teams folder. This unique logo is the primary representation of the project and expresses its distinct visual character. See Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 - NINFA logo

Furthermore, the EU flag and the following disclaimer (Figure 2) will be present in all forms of communication.

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Figure 2 - EU Flag & Disclaimer

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2.2 Ninfa colours

The NINFA colour schemes shown in Figure 3 are the two colours used in the logo and can be utilized throughout the project materials to organize and emphasize various sections of content.

These colours will also influence the colour scheme of all other communication materials (templates, leaflets, rollup banner, social media platforms, articles)

Figure 3 - NINFA LOGO colours

2.3 Ninfa Templates

CETRI has created a number of NINFA templates in order to maintain consistency in the layout and appearance of all project uses. The templates that have been developed so far are:

- **NINFA Deliverable template** to ensure that all project Deliverables will have homogenous format. The font and colours used in the text will match those used in the NINFA logo creating consistent visual identity of the project. Also, all Public Deliverables will be uploaded on the website so interested stakeholders can easily access and download them. This can promote transparency, and knowledge sharing, which are important values in European projects.
- **NINFA agenda** to support the consortium in the organization of events. An agenda can provide potential attendees with a clear idea of what will be covered during the event, the timing of different sessions, and who will be speaking or presenting. Making the agenda available online can also make it easier to share and promote the event through social media channels, email, or newsletters. This can help increase the visibility of the event and reach a wider audience.
- **NINFA minutes** to help keep track of what was discussed and decided. It can also help partners who were absent to stay informed. Sharing the notes with everyone involved in the project can ensure that all partners are on the same page and can contribute to achieving the project's goals.
- **NINFA Powerpoint presentation** to ensure consistency in the overall look of the presentations while still allowing partners to add their own content and tailor their presentations to their specific needs and audiences.

All the templates feature the project logo, the EU flag and disclaimer, and the NINFA colours and text font. They can be found in the EXT-NINFA Teams folder. In order to utilize the templates as effective communication tools, it is important for all partners to use the correct templates for their intended purposes.

2.4 NINFA leaflet

CETRI has produced a NINFA leaflet to be distributed at conferences and other relevant events related to groundwater management and protection, across EU countries.

The project leaflet is a key communication component and should accompany project partners at all communication-related activities. It will serve as the first outreach document of the project that provides an insight into the core objectives, the challenges, the concept, partners, and EU funding programme.

The leaflet is threefold and it includes: 1) project logo, title and website, 2) partners logos, 3) project information, 4) social media platforms, 5) the challenge, 6) the solution and 7) who benefits. It is presented below in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - NINFA leaflet hard copy

Furthermore, as the project continues to advance, more promotional materials will be developed to portray the research done, the new findings and any related news. Such as:

- A rollup banner will be designed to be set up in future conferences and workshops.
- A poster will soon be developed to be used in workshops or any other event the partners will attend. It can be designed in line with the specific event.
- Videos and podcasts with project information and interviews will be produced.
- NINFA Best practices Handbook” will be delivered to ensure that best practices, lessons learnt, and recommendations are clearly and effectively understood in the groundwater community.
- Extra promotional material will be needed due to clustering activities with sister projects.
- e-Newsletter will be published every six months summarising all activities related to the project and targeting the research and academic community, water industry, policymakers. SOILGUARD newsletters will contain articles on latest research and technology

3. Website

The NINFA website (www.ninfa-project.eu) has been launched since the beginning of the project by CETRI. The website structure and design are presented below in Table 1.

Website Overview

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Home	Project	Outputs	Communication & Dissemination	Newsletter	Sister Projects	News
	Objective	Public Deliverables	Publications			
	Structure		Conferences			
	Partners		Videos			
			Gallery			
			Promotional Material			

Table 1 – NINFA website structure

As the project develops, the website will undergo frequent updates with continuous contribution from the partners. The latest developments will be shared through newsletters, press releases, research outputs, and deliverables, all available on the project website. These updates aim to generate interest and engage with diverse sectors of society.

The website contains links to the social account platform on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. All public deliverables generated for the project will be accessible to all and easy to download them.

To track the impact of the website through the number of visitors, google analytics has been enabled and will be monitored continuously. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be discussed in detail in the Deliverable D6.2 “Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDEC) “.

The NINFA homepage is shown as screenshots in Annex 1.

4. Social media channels

It is important to develop a social media strategy in order to promote the NINFA project effectively. CETRI has started to create posts (kick-off meeting material mostly) and with the increased contribution of the partners the activity of the channels will grow further.

Posts will be designed to encourage people to like or follow the NINFA pages and to increase the awareness and interest on the development of the project.

Visual content, such as images and videos, can be more engaging and memorable than text-based content and can help tell the story of the NINFA project. Followers will be encouraged to share their own content related to the NINFA project in their websites and personal channels. This can include photos, videos, or testimonials.

An increased engagement with the target audience will be to respond/react to comments, messages and mentions on NINFA's social media channels building also a stronger relationship. By using social media channels, the communication becomes more direct and personal than many other forms of communication (newspaper, radio, television).

To identify which aspects of the strategy are effective and reaching out to the audience, it is necessary to monitor and measure: a) for **website analytics**, google analytics will be used to track the number of visitors to the website, their location, how long they spend on the website, and what pages they visit. b) for **social media analytics**, the analytics tools provided by each platform will be used to track engagement metrics like likes, shares, and comments. If the effectiveness is not satisfactory then different approaches will be considered.

NINFA will use four different social media platforms to target different stakeholder groups: LinkedIn Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Profiles have been created and are presented below in Figure 5 with a link to the specific web address.

Figure 5 - Social media profiles

All partners are encouraged to follow and share the above NINFA social media accounts in order to promote the project and to broaden the NINFA community. CETRI is responsible for ensuring the profiles remain up to date and active with news and relevant posts during and after the project lifetime.

The social media platforms are linked to the NINFA website and vice versa. When a website has more links pointing to it from other reputable websites, it signals to search engines that the content on the site is valuable and trustworthy. Linking a website to its social media pages and vice versa can help increase the number of links pointing to the site and improve its search engine rankings.

One of the benefits of social media is that it allows people to connect and communicate with others from all over the world, to participate in discussions on a wide range of topics and also learn and grow from the diverse perspectives and viewpoints of each other. The use of hashtags helps in this sense and several are incorporated into NINFA's posts such as #groundwater, #watercycle, #hydrology, #groundwatermanagement, #horizoneurope. Furthermore, the tag on the NINFA project should always be used on all four social media profiles. (Figure 5, i.e.: @ninfa-project)

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, WP6 leader CETRI, has created several promotional materials and has made plans to develop even more in the future.

Throughout the course of the project, the website will be updated frequently with input from all partners involved. These updates will be disseminated through various channels such as newsletters, press releases, research outputs, and deliverables.

The consortium aims to utilize a variety of materials in combination with website content, social media activity, conference organization/participation, publications, and other initiatives to establish a robust community around NINFA, which will ensure the success of the project's expected outcomes.

Annex 1

NINFA Home Page

Partners

Annex 2

PowerPoint Template

Taking action to prevent and mitigate pollution of groundwater bodies

Presentation Title

Person Name
Person Organization Name
Location

Date of presentation

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Title here

Task X.X: Title (Mx-Mxx) Leader: XX.
Contributors: xx, xxx, xx

OBJECTIVE 1
To help give your audience an overview, this section can include a brief description of the goal, its relevance to your sector or industry, and the specific sub-targets your organization is addressing.

OBJECTIVE 2
To help give your audience an overview, this section can include a brief description of the goal, its relevance to your sector or industry, and the specific sub-targets your organization is addressing.

OBJECTIVE 3
To help give your audience an overview, this section can include a brief description of the goal, its relevance to your sector or industry, and the specific sub-targets your organization is addressing.

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Conclusion

End your presentation with a review of the highlights, and a renewed commitment to continue working on next steps.

A vision statement, call-to-action are powerful ways to conclude your progress. Leave your audience inspired, and motivated to help your organization achieve its goals!

End your presentation with a review of the highlights, and a renewed commitment to continue working on next steps.

A vision statement, call-to-action are powerful ways to conclude your progress. Leave your audience inspired, and motivated to help your organization achieve its goals!

HIGHLIGHT 1 Summarize the key points here.
• Bullet points help!
• Bullet points help!

HIGHLIGHT 2 Summarize the key points here.
• Bullet points help!
• Bullet points help!

HIGHLIGHT 3 Summarize the key points here.
• Bullet points help!
• Bullet points help!

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